

Eigenvalues of Circulant Matrices and Rank-One Perturbations: A Survey

Ishpreet Kaur

January 2026

Abstract

Circulant matrices form an important class of structured matrices whose spectral properties can be described explicitly using the discrete Fourier transform. In this survey, we review the eigenvalue structure of circulant matrices with real entries and examine how rank-one perturbations affect their spectra. A simple illustrative example is included to demonstrate the stability and variation of eigenvalues under low-rank modifications.

1 Introduction

Linear algebra is a powerful mathematical theory. It is the mathematics of the modern technological world of complex multivariable systems and computers. In linear algebra, circulant matrices form a structured class of matrices that play an important role in the study of linear transformations and spectral theory.

A circulant matrix is a special type of Toeplitz matrix in which each row is obtained by a cyclic shift of the previous row. The circulant matrix is diagonalizable using the discrete Fourier transform [1]. The diagonal-constant structure of the matrix plays an important role in linear algebra and functional analysis [2].

A perturbed matrix is obtained by adding a low-rank modification to a given Toeplitz matrix. Rank-one perturbations are important because they allow a detailed analysis of changes in spectral properties [4].

In this paper, I present a survey of known results on the eigenvalues of circulant matrices and their rank-one perturbations. The focus is on how this quantity change under perturbation, illustrated through a simple example.

2 Preliminaries

2.1 Notation

Throughout this paper, \mathbb{R} denotes the field of real numbers and $\mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ denotes the set of all $n \times n$ real matrices. The identity matrix of order n is denoted by

I_n , or simply by I when the dimension is clear from the context.

For a matrix $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, its set of eigenvalues is denoted by $\{\lambda_1(A), \lambda_2(A), \dots, \lambda_n(A)\}$, counted with algebraic multiplicities. The set of all eigenvalues is known as a spectrum. The rank of a matrix A is denoted by $\text{rank}(A)$.

The n th root of unity is denoted by $\omega_n = e^{2\pi i/n}$.

Throughout this work, circulant matrices are assumed to have real entries, while their eigenvalues may be real or complex and are considered over the complex field.

2.2 Circulant Matrices

Circulant matrices form a well-studied class of structured matrices and play an important role in both theoretical and applied linear algebra. A key feature of circulant matrices is that they are completely determined by their first row, and all other rows are obtained by cyclic permutations [1, 2].

Definition 1. A matrix $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is called a *circulant matrix* if it has the form

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} a_0 & a_1 & a_2 & \cdots & a_{n-1} \\ a_{n-1} & a_0 & a_1 & \cdots & a_{n-2} \\ a_{n-2} & a_{n-1} & a_0 & \cdots & a_{n-3} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_1 & a_2 & a_3 & \cdots & a_0 \end{pmatrix},$$

where $a_0, a_1, \dots, a_{n-1} \in \mathbb{R}$. Each row of a circulant matrix is obtained by a cyclic shift of the previous row [1].

One of the most important properties of circulant matrices is that they are diagonalizable by the discrete Fourier transform matrix [1].

2.3 Rank-One Perturbed Matrices

A rank-one perturbed matrix is obtained by adding a rank-one matrix to a given matrix.

Definition 2. A rank-one perturbed matrix is a matrix of the form

$$\tilde{A} = A + uv^T,$$

where A is an $n \times n$ real matrix and $u, v \in \mathbb{R}^n$. The matrix uv^T has rank one and represents a rank-one perturbation of A [4].

3 Eigenvalues of Circulant Matrices

3.1 General Eigenvalue Formula

Let

$$A = \text{circ}(a_0, a_1, \dots, a_{n-1})$$

be an $n \times n$ circulant matrix, where each row is obtained by a cyclic shift of the previous row. It is well known that the eigenvalues of A are given by

$$\lambda_k = \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} a_j \omega_n^{jk}, \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, n-1,$$

where $\omega_n = e^{2\pi i/n}$ denotes a primitive n th root of unity. Hence, the eigenvalues of a circulant matrix are precisely the discrete Fourier transform of its first row [1, 2].

3.2 Spectral Properties

Important properties of eigenvalues of circulant matrices follow directly from the formula above:

3.2.1 Diagonalizability

Every circulant matrix is diagonalizable by the discrete Fourier matrix [1].

3.2.2 Symmetry of spectrum

When the circulant matrix is symmetric then all eigenvalues are real [3].

3.2.3 Multiplicity

Eigenvalue multiplicities depend on the structure of the first row. However, repeated values in the discrete Fourier transform lead to repeated eigenvalues [3].

3.2.4 Computational efficiency

Large matrices can be computed using Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) algorithms [2].

These properties make circulant matrices applicable for signal processing, numerical linear algebra, and image analysis.

3.3 Illustrative Example

To demonstrate the eigenvalue structure, consider a simple example.

Example (3×3 circulant matrix). Let

$$A = \text{circ}(a_0, a_1, a_2).$$

The eigenvalues of A are given by

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_0 &= a_0 + a_1 + a_2, \\ \lambda_1 &= a_0 + a_1\omega_3 + a_2\omega_3^2, \quad \lambda_2 = a_0 + a_1\omega_3^2 + a_2\omega_3, \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\omega_3 = e^{2\pi i/3}.$$

3.4 Eigenvalues of a 3×3 Circulant Matrix and DFT

Consider the circulant matrix

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 3 & 1 & 2 \\ 2 & 3 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Let the first row be $(a_0, a_1, a_2) = (1, 2, 3)$. For an $n \times n$ circulant matrix, the eigenvalues are given by

$$\lambda_k = \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} a_j \omega^{jk}, \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, n-1,$$

where $\omega = e^{2\pi i/n}$ is a primitive n th root of unity.

For $n = 3$, $\omega = e^{2\pi i/3} = -\frac{1}{2} + i\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}$. Hence,

$$\lambda_0 = 1 + 2 + 3 = 6,$$

$$\lambda_1 = 1 + 2\omega + 3\omega^2 = -\frac{3}{2} - i\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2},$$

$$\lambda_2 = 1 + 2\omega^2 + 3\omega = -\frac{3}{2} + i\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}.$$

Thus, the spectrum of A is

$$\sigma(A) = \left\{ 6, -\frac{3}{2} \pm i\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \right\}.$$

It is well known that the eigenvalues of a circulant matrix are given by the discrete Fourier transform of its first row, and that circulant matrices are diagonalized by the Fourier matrix [2, 1].

4 Eigenvalues of Rank-One Perturbed Circulant Matrices

Let $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$. A matrix \tilde{A} is called a *rank-one perturbed matrix* of A if

$$\tilde{A} = A + uv^T,$$

for some vectors $u, v \in \mathbb{R}^n$. The matrix uv^T has rank one and represents a rank-one perturbation of A .

4.1 Illustrative Example

Consider the circulant matrix

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 3 & 1 & 2 \\ 2 & 3 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Since each row of A contains the same entries in a different order, the sum of each row is equal to 6. Consequently,

$$A \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = 6 \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix},$$

which shows that 6 is an eigenvalue of A .

Now consider the rank-one perturbed matrix

$$\tilde{A} = A + uv^T,$$

where

$$u = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad v = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

We compute

$$uv^T \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = u \left((\alpha \ 0 \ 0) \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \right) = \alpha \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Hence,

$$\tilde{A} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = (6 + \alpha) \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix},$$

and therefore $6 + \alpha$ is an eigenvalue of the perturbed matrix \tilde{A} .

The eigenvalues $-\frac{3}{2} \pm i\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}$ remain unchanged under the rank-one perturbation and are the same as those of the original circulant matrix. Therefore,

$$\text{spec}(\tilde{A}) = \left\{ 6 + \alpha, -\frac{3}{2} \pm i\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \right\}.$$

This example illustrates how a rank-one perturbation affects the spectrum of a circulant matrix [3, 4].

4.2 Effects of Perturbation on Eigenvalues

4.2.1 Loss of circulant structure

Although A is circulant, its perturbed matrix \tilde{A} is generally not. Consequently, \tilde{A} is no longer diagonalized by the Fourier matrix. The discrete Fourier transform formula for the eigenvalues no longer applies [4].

4.2.2 Low-rank effect

Most eigenvalues move only slightly, while at most one eigenvalue may experience a comparatively larger shift [4].

4.2.3 Real–complex behavior

Although both A and \tilde{A} are real matrices, their eigenvalues may still be complex. In such cases, the complex eigenvalues occur in conjugate pairs. If the rank-one perturbation preserves symmetry, when $u = v$, then the perturbed matrix remains symmetric and all eigenvalues are real [3].

5 Conclusion

In this paper, I presented a survey of the eigenvalue structure of a 3×3 circulant matrix and examined how this spectral property is affected by rank-one perturbations. I focused on circulant matrices with real entries and reviewed eigenvalue representation based on roots of unity.

I further discussed the effects of rank-one perturbations, highlighting the loss of circulant structure, the stability of most eigenvalues under low-rank modifications, and the special behavior observed in the symmetric case. Circulant and perturbed circulant matrices appear in many applications, such as signal and image processing, numerical methods for partial differential equations. Understanding their spectral behavior is therefore important for both theoretical and practical computations.

References

- [1] Philip J. Davis. *Circulant Matrices*. Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1979.
- [2] Robert M. Gray. *Toeplitz and Circulant Matrices: A Review*. Now Publishers, 2006.

- [3] Roger A. Horn and Charles R. Johnson. *Matrix Analysis*. Cambridge University Press, 2 edition, 2013.
- [4] G. W. Stewart and Ji-guang Sun. *Matrix Perturbation Theory*. Academic Press, 1990.